

PRICKETT

PEABODY MUSEUM

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November 5th 1984

Dear Bill

It was great to see you last weekend -- you are certainly looking healthy and prospering!

Enclosed is a synthesis of my info. on the whereabouts of the Marv Dacht material; also a copy of the article Edith was lecturing on -- as I thought it might prove of interest ?? someday.

I'm in the midst of the last mad rush to get it all together for a mid Dec. blast off. On top of the academic struggle, I can't imagine anything worse than cramming all of

one's life into boxes
yet again!

Should you ever get the
wild urge in the next 2 years
to laze on the beaches of
Serendib -- or to wallow in the
archaeology (?) of Buddhist
shrines and tombs beyond the
saturation point (many of the
sites are indeed superbly beautiful
do get in touch -- I will be
contactable c/o S. U. Peraniyaga's

Archaeological Survey Dept

Sir Marcus Fernando R.C.

Colombo 7 Sri Lanka

or my home address -- 'at least for
a few months will be --

26 Guildford Crescent

Colombo 7, Sri Lanka

Tel: 011-94-1-91076

With all best wishes,

Markus

FROM M. PRIUETT

Marv Dasht Material in the A.G. Williamson Survey Collections, as noted Sept. 1975

SHIRAZ:

7 drawers in Shiraz of 18 drawers containing AGW Survey stuff were marked "Marv Dasht"

- 1) "crates 1 & 2"
- 2) "crates 2 & 3"
- 3) "crates 4 & 5"
- 4) "crates 6 & 7"
- 5) "crates 10 & 12"
- 6 & 7) 2 just "M.D."

I have no idea how full they were, but they probably were not empty since I listed the empty but labelled drawers (8 additional others) separately.

TEHERAN:

There were 35 crates of AGW pottery which Stronach sent to Iran Bastan when the Institute moved. Henry later told me he saw a big mass of it in the Museum (?basement) all together as the Williamson Survey collection. I don't think the numbers were on the crates, but just for my enumeration convenience, 5 of the crates are listed in my notes as having M.D. stuff.

(It had been arranged in Bagher's that I would come out & publish it. Henry says they had arranged the air to check everything)

Crate

- 1) Marv Dasht sites:

303	419	218
722 & 723	546	551
691	214	651
207	547	Chinese Teah (?Sic)
204	531	20-57 & Siraf

- 19) M.D. 365

Marv Dasht Misc.

The other bags in this crate were:

- 6D
- E sites stone bowls and slag
- Sirjan B 10 glass
- Bone (?bone) Sirjan Excavation Material Various Levels
- Brick ?Sirjan Surface
- B 10 reconstructibles
- Well-preserved castle near SS
- Sirjan ~~10~~ 11 12 mixed wall
- Chah Hak kilns 3
- Var. h-sites green glaze bowls (Sass?) type
- Chah Hak kiln ②
- Lalezar

- 29) Marv Dasht misc. includes:

- stone
 - interesting sherds
 - moulded
 - 800's painted
 - Qaleh Istakhr
 - MD (?) labelled sherds
 - MD moulded ware - various sites
 - MD in general or Q. Istakhr (probably)
- (was tied together with them)

30) All Istakhr
W, A, K, L, C, R, I, F; G -3 bags
Rampart; near guard hut

31) Marv Dasht:
371
SW 3 (or ?543)
668
800's
300's
370
562

Also in the crate were:

Kirman?
Daulatabad 1
Ramrod
Stone bowls K sites
Atish Kadeh
Daulatabad ②

I have no idea if these were complete or partial collections of the listed sites -- may be either or both. In general, the stuff in Teheran was material of greater interest to him than that in Shiraz, and that in England even more so, but the interest trajectories could have been on any one of about a half dozen different problems so I can't second guess what's actually there. I am, however, almost certain that none of the Marv Dasht material was taken to Siraz and left there as "dead storage" (where a lot of the lower priority coastal material was deposited) since he considered the material to be yours, to be from central Fars not the coast, and still had some problems he wanted to work on.

P.S. He has a lot of kilns and kiln material from a place called Chah Pak. I'm pretty sure it's not from when I was with him. Thus it is probably either from interior Fars or Kirman (city to Narmashir area) or Sistan. Does that place name ring any bells with you?